

ASTRONOMY

A NEW LOOK AT THE VORTEX DYNAMICS OF MATTER IN THE UNIVERSE

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Abstract

Modern science, at the present stage of civilization's development, describes the origin of the Universe (time and space) as the result of the Big Bang from some super-dense "point" (as a "primeval atom" [1]) approximately 13.7 billion years ago. It is believed that from the moment of this explosion the Universe began to expand, and that later stars, galaxies, nebulae, and planets formed from enormous clouds of intergalactic gas produced by the explosion as a result of their gravitational collapse; all this is considered to be sufficiently well explained by observational facts. Over the past 40 years, more advanced telescopes with greatly enhanced capabilities, as well as other observational instruments placed beyond the Earth's atmosphere, have made it possible to obtain clearer high-resolution images of cosmic objects in various regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. This makes it possible to reconsider the accumulated observational material from a new perspective. Based on the hypothesis proposed and developed by us - that the principal form of existence of matter in the Universe is a liquid, rotating, self-contained spherical vortex, whose internal dynamics are responsible for all types of electromagnetic radiation across different spectral regions [2-4] - we analyzed the accumulated observational material concerning various manifestations of the state of matter in the cosmic space surrounding us. Observational data for 7,835 objects included in the New General Catalogue (NGC), presented on various Internet sites, were reanalyzed.

Keywords: vortex, radiation, vortical state, astrophysics.

1. WHAT DO OBSERVATIONAL FACTS SHOW US?

All observational facts in astronomy are based on the detection of radiation fluxes of different wavelengths emitted by the objects under study. As is well known, the atoms that make up these objects emit light only in an excited state; in a cold state they are incapable of emitting it. Therefore, matter whose atoms are in a cold state - for example, in the form of planets and their satellites - is visible to us only due to reflected or scattered light emitted by other objects. This fact indicates that all the magnificent observable structures of matter in the Universe - such as galaxies, nebulae, stars, and comets - are formed by matter concentrated in compact structures, a portion of whose atoms are in an excited state. At the same time, the luminosity of an object depends on the degree of its excitation, i.e., on its energetic state. Another interesting fact is that all objects in the Universe emit their radiation radially and uniformly in all directions, just as our Sun does. However, even in the case of the Sun, we do not see the rays emitted in planes perpendicular to our line of sight. As a result, we perceive it not as a "hedgehog" radiating light in all directions, but simply as a luminous disk. Its radial emissions can be observed only during an eclipse by the Moon or with the aid of a coronagraph. Likewise, we do not directly observe the radial radiation emitted by other objects in the Universe.

On the other hand, the fact that light from sources located billions of light-years away reaches us indicates that the region of the Universe through which the light from the observed object travels to us is essentially empty; that is, there is no matter capable of absorbing the light. In other words, the deep vacuum between individual objects that concentrate matter is relatively

empty and transparent. The best evidence for this comes from data obtained with the Hubble Space Telescope. Orbiting the Earth through outer space, the telescope observes and studies objects that cannot be detected from Earth because of the interfering effects of the atmosphere. During its 19 years of operation, "Hubble" discovered so many new phenomena in the Universe that several thousand scientific articles have already been required merely to describe its observations. One of the most important discoveries is the enormous, almost completely empty region in the constellation Eridanus, detected by the Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP). This "void" contains nothing - not even the relic microwave radiation that is believed to have originated during the earliest stage of the Universe and still exists today, revealing itself through a temperature of approximately 2.7 K [5]. Yet here there is complete zero. Moreover, this "nothingness" extends across a billion light-years. Researchers were astonished, since nothing like this had ever been observed before. These observations challenge many modern concepts concerning the structure of the Universe

Observations show that the bulk of the matter we observe in nature is concentrated in stars, which differ in mass and luminosity and which, in turn, are grouped into galaxies — giant systems of enormous size, mass, and luminosity that also differ significantly from one another. More than two-thirds of the visible mass of the Universe is contained in galaxies, more than 70% of which are spiral galaxies.

However, it is precisely the spiral arms of galaxies that contain an enhanced concentration of diffuse matter composed of ionized and molecular gas filling the interstellar space within them, although the total mass of this diffuse substance is small compared with

the total mass of the stars. At the same time, the galaxies themselves are isolated, compact, and closed systems. The concentration of diffuse matter in the spiral arms of galaxies exceeds the concentration of the cosmic background surrounding the galaxies by several times. Therefore, there are no grounds for claiming that

galaxies actively consume the surrounding gas flowing along their arms toward the nucleus and use it as building material. This conclusion coincides with the conclusion reached by Viktor Ambartsumian as early as 1958 in his report on the evolution of galaxies [6–10], presented at the Solvay Conference.

Fig. 1. Appearance of Comet 17P/Holmes, October 2007 [11].

All cosmic objects are isolated from one another. However, luminosity variations are often observed in some cosmic objects (short- and long-period variable stars, Cepheids, novae and supernovae, and comets). The causes that give rise to these variations, as well as the changes occurring in the external appearance of the radiating object, have not yet been sufficiently studied.

On October 23–24, 2007, an astonishing and unprecedented cosmic event occurred in space. **Comet 17P/Holmes**, normally visible only through a telescope and moving quietly along its orbit, suddenly flared up (exploded). Within just a few hours, its brightness first increased by 400,000 times and then by a million times. The causes of this phenomenon remain a mystery.

Another remarkable mystery associated with the comet's explosion is the perfectly symmetrical, spherical shape of the cloud (Fig. 1), which is clearly visible in the image obtained by the Hubble Space Telescope [11]. Astronomers calculated that material was ejected from the comet at a speed of about 2,000 kilometers per hour. According to A. Fitzsimmons, the total volume of material expelled during this outburst reached about 1% of the comet's mass, comparable to a situation in which the Earth suddenly ejected its entire crust into space [12]. At the same time, the expelled matter did not disperse but remained within the comet's gravitational field. The nature of such a highly symmetrical explosion has likewise not yet received an explanation.

The observational data presented above for the comet indicate the nonlocal nature of the process that led to the explosion - the entire nucleus of the comet exploded as a single whole. Contemporary models of cometary nuclei as conglomerates of ice and rock do not provide convincing explanations for the processes that could have caused the explosion of the cometary nucleus.

Even more mysterious is the fact that 17P/Holmes has exploded more than once. It was originally discovered in 1892 by Edwin Holmes following a similar outburst. In December 1892, the comet faded considerably and became observable only through a telescope. By mid-December, its brightness was estimated at about 11m, while the diameter of its coma was 3–4 arcminutes. On January 16, 1893, a powerful flare-up was recorded: the comet again became visible to the naked eye, reaching a reaching an apparent magnitude of 5–6. A bright nucleus of magnitude 7–8m was observed in the comet. In the final days of January, the comet again faded to 11–12m. The comet continued to be observed until April, when it was visible only through large telescopes. However, in February, the Austrian astronomer Johann Holetschek recorded another smaller outburst, during which the comet became visible through a 15-centimeter telescope (9–10m).

The above-mentioned changes in cometary brightness are not isolated cases. The brightness of the short-period **Comet Tuttle-Giacobini-Kresák** suddenly increased by nearly 10 stellar magnitudes (about 10,000 times!) two days before its perihelion passage in 1973. It then gradually decreased over the course of a month, but on July 6, 1973, another powerful outburst occurred. Significant abrupt increases in brightness (approximately 250 times) were also observed for **29P/Schwassmann-Wachmann**. These data indicate not some local process, but rather that the entire nucleus of the comet responded as a single whole. Other phenomena are also observed that are difficult to reconcile with the generally accepted view of cometary nuclei as primordial Solar System material in the form of frozen conglomerates of ice and dust.

Fig. 2. Comet Hale-Bopp

On the picture it is shown not less 7 jets, owing out from the coma of Comet Hale-Bopp [12].

Thus, **Comet Hale-Bopp** exhibited intense activity even at a great distance from the Sun in the form of numerous jets (or streamers). In the image of the comet (Fig. 2), no fewer than seven jets can be seen being ejected from the comet's coma, and no preferred direction of the eruptive emissions is observed [13].

The nucleus of **Halley's Comet**, during its perihelion passage in 1986, ejected a dust cloud extending over hundreds of thousands of kilometers.

On March 27, 1996, the X-ray satellite ROSAT

unexpectedly detected X-ray radiation emitted by **Comet Hyakutake**.

Images of cometary surfaces obtained in recent years with the aid of spacecraft also do not correspond to the presumed conglomerate of ice and rock. Of the 111.5 square kilometers of the surface area of **Tempel 1**, according to data from Peter Schultz of Brown University, only three regions, with a total area of merely 2.8 hectares, are covered with frozen water mixed with dirt. All the remaining surface is covered by a layer of dust. At the same time, numerous small craters are visible on the comet's surface.

Fig.3. a) The nucleus of comet **Wild 2** [14]; b) Intense streams of gas and dust surround the nucleus of **81P/Wild 2**, one of the most active bodies in the Solar System [15].

The first photographs of the surface of **81P/Wild** transmitted by the Stardust reveal an even greater diversity of landscape, showing peaks, depressions, craters of various sizes, and active jets streaming from the surface in different directions [14–16].

Particularly unusual is the fact that the comet possesses virtually none of the small craters observed on **Tempel 1**, while only large craters are present, whose age, according to Donald Brownlee, amounts to several billion years [17].

Fig. 4. a) This is an artist's concept depicting a view of comet Wild 2 as seen from NASA's Stardust spacecraft during its flyby of the comet on Jan. 2, 2004 [16]; b) Comet Tempel 1's Electrifying Impact [17].

By examining approximately two dozen dust particles (out of about one million) captured from the comet [18–20], scientists discovered minerals such as olivine, pyroxene, and spinel, which normally form at temperatures exceeding 1000°C and are quite commonly found on Earth among crystals of deep mantle origin.

Changes in the luminosity of comets and supernova explosions, the appearance of expanding spherical shells in planetary nebulae (Figs. 5–6), and the emergence of zones of different luminosity similar to those observed when

*Fig. 5. Spherical shapes of outer shells:
a) Comet Holmes [21], b) Sun [22], c) Abell Nebula 39 [23],
d) NGC 3587 M97 Owl Nebula [24].*

the potential of a central body changes, leading to the formation of spherical strata of spherical shape (Figs. 7b, c, d), suggest changes in the charge state of

the object. As was shown in our works [2–4], the cause of this is a change in the object's rotational velocity about its own axis.

Fig. 6. V838 Monocerotis [25]

The abrupt change in the luminosity of **Comet 17P/Holmes** and the formation around it of spherical zones resembling equipotential surfaces formed around charged bodies indicate the existence of common properties between the matter of the cometary nucleus and

the atoms constituting charged bodies at the centers of spherical strata. The observed phenomena make it possible to assume that the basis of the volume of cometary nuclei — as well as of any cosmic objects, including atoms of chemical elements and

*Fig. 7. Spherical forms of shells:
a – Comet Holmes [26], b – d – spherical striations at the central charged body [27]*

elementary particles - is a unified liquid, viscous, dense matter forming a self-contained isolated vortex capable of responding sensitively to changes in external conditions created by various cosmic objects. This conclusion corresponds more closely to the observed phenomena than the conventional concept of cometary nuclei as conglomerates of ice and rock.

2. EVOLUTION OF GALAXIES

Fluctuations in luminosity have been observed only in relatively small objects of the Universe. Galaxies are undoubtedly also subject to similar luminosity variations. However, given the billions of years over

which galaxies exist, we are unable to detect such changes directly in objects of this scale. Nevertheless, the presence of diffuse envelopes in elliptical galaxies (spherical envelopes in elliptical galaxies of type E) surrounding the central galactic nucleus - which, as studies of various kinds of galaxies show, are present in all galaxy types — indicates that at some time in the past the galactic nucleus underwent strong excitation and, similarly to 17P/Holmes, ejected part of its mass. The excited galactic nucleus, like 17P/Holmes, continued its motion and left the region where

*Fig. 8. Stages in the transformation of elliptical galaxies during their evolution from E to S0:
a - NGC 7144 [28]; b - NGC 3379 E1 [29]; c - NGC 221 E2 [30]; d - NGC 533 E3 [31]; e - NGC 4697 E4 [32];
f - NGC 584 E5 [33]; g - NGC 3610 E6 [34]; h - NGC 4026 S0 [35].*

the excitation had occurred. Subsequently, lacking an external energy supply to maintain its excited state,

the galaxy began to evolve, which was reflected primarily in changes in its external appearance. In order to conserve its acquired angular momentum, the galaxy

began to elongate along its axis of rotation while simultaneously increasing its rotational velocity about its own axis. Gradually, it transformed from a spherical

form into an elliptical one rotating around its major axis.

Fig. 9. Formation of polar bars in galactic nuclei:
a - NGC 3867 [36]; b - NGC 108 [37]; c - NGC 4572 [38].

Further elongation led, through the stages of morphological transformation noted by Edwin Hubble, from E1 to S0 galaxies (Fig. 8), to the formation of elongated bars at the poles of the rotating central spherical mass (Fig. 9). These bars, as we assume, are continuations of the poles from whose ends the outflow of matter from the nucleus began, creating streams of opposite polarity, similar to the model presented in [3, 39–40] (Fig. 10).

The matter flowing out from the elongated polar bars (Fig. 10b) represents a continuation of two internal

axial vortices that form not only the poles but also the central core of the rotating mass of matter, and which possess opposite directions of not only translational but also rotational motion of the matter within them.

In accordance with Helmholtz's second law, these ends of the vortex tend to reconnect with the nucleus that emitted them (Figs. 11, 12). The figures show different stages of the outflow of matter from the polar bars.

Fig. 10. a) A model of formation of streams of liquid in rotating liquid spherical vortex, stipulated the appearance of poles and magnetic force lines [3]; b) A model of appearance of bulge, bars - poles and arms with different directions of rotation. (Milyuvne, etc, the given work, 2008 [3, 39, 40, 91]).

The appearance of bars in the central nuclei of galaxies, in turn, indicates the high viscosity of the matter composing galactic nuclei, as a result of which they are

unable to rapidly shed matter in the equatorial region in order to slow their increasingly rapid rotation. This, in turn, casts doubt on the

Fig. 11. Different stages of matter ejection from the polar bars of galactic nuclei:
a - NGC 3782 SBcd [41]; b - NGC 3509 SBbc [42]; c - NGC 1720 SBab [43]; d - NGC 7479 SBc [44]; e - NGC 6701 SBa [45]; f - NGC 762 SBa [46]; g - NGC 2935 SBb [47]; h - NGC 6782 SBa [48].

possibility of the instantaneous dispersion (within 10–33 seconds) of the matter of the Universe from a single initial point, as proposed by the Big Bang

hypothesis [53]. The differing degrees of spread of the spiral arms are apparently related to the rotational velocity of the galactic nucleus itself about its axis.

Fig. 12. Patterns of different types of spiral arm development in galaxies:
a - NGC 5383 SBb [49]; b - NGC 986 [50]; c - NGC 2442 SBbc [51]; d - NGC 1300 SBbc [52].

Sometimes the outflowing matter succeeds in reconnecting with the opposite pole. This leads to the

formation of ellipsoidal galaxies similar to those shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Closed polar outflows in elliptical galaxies:
a - NGC 2859 SB0-a [54]; b - NGC 1269 SB0-a [55]; c - NGC 4643 SB0-a [56].

In other cases, however, the terminal vortices, due to the high velocities of the matter at their ends, are unable to approach the opposite pole and pass by it. In this

way, structures with complex systems of twisted spiral arms are formed in galaxies (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Different patterns of spiral arm twisting in galaxies:
a - NGC 4440 SBa [57]; b - NGC 1433 SBa [58]; c - NGC 266 SBab [59]; d - NGC 3992 SBbc [60]; e - NGC 3351 M95 SBb [61].

The differing lengths of the spiral arms are apparently determined by the length of time the galaxy

remains in such a state. An ellipsoidal region is always observed in the central parts of galaxies.

Fig. 15. Polar ejections of matter in planetary nebulae:
a - NGC 5307 [62]; b - NGC 6543 [63].

An ellipsoidal region with arms from which matter is expelled is observed not only in galaxies but also in planetary nebulae (Fig. 15). This indicates the existence of common laws governing the dynamics of matter in different objects throughout the Universe.

Sometimes the velocities of matter outflow from the polar regions are so high that the spiral arms

are unable to reconnect with the nucleus of the galaxy that emitted them. In such cases, they are expelled far into cosmic space (Fig.16). Their superposition with similar outflows from other galaxies forms peculiar streams that become sources of excitation for other objects encountered along their paths — stars, comets, supernovae, variable stars, and even galaxies themselves.

Fig. 16. Formation of elongated outflow arms in galaxies:
a - NGC 1365 [64]; b - NGC 6872 SBb/P [65]; c - UGC 10214 [66].

The outflow of matter from the polar regions is simultaneously accompanied by its dissipation, beginning at the ends of the bars, into smaller individual

masses that give rise to all classes of stars observed within the spiral arms (Fig.17).

Fig. 17. Dissipation (decay) of expelled matter into individual stars:
a - NGC 1300 [67]; b - NGC 5194 M51 [68].

Fig. 18. Patterns of luminosity of matter expelled from galaxies: NGC 4736:
a - NGC 4736 visible region; b - NGC 4736 ultraviolet region [69]

Since the polar outflows simultaneously serve as sources of magnetic field lines [39–40, 91], the penetration of the expelled matter forming stars within the

spiral arms by these fields, which carry angular momentum, leads to a greater spin-up of the stars, i.e., to a higher degree of excitation than that observed in the vicinity of the galactic bulge (Fig. 18).

Fig. 19. Appearance of fine diffuse dispersed matter in the spiral arms of galaxies:
a - NGC 4319 SBab [70]; b - NGC 1350 SBab [71].

This, in turn, serves as the cause not only of the enhanced luminosity of stars in the spiral arms and in certain regions of spiral galaxies (Figs. 17, 18), but also of the ejection of matter by these stars, leading to the appearance of diffuse dark dusty matter in these regions of the arms. The expelled mass of the spiral arms expands, forming peculiar “wings” within which the central ellipsoidal bulge appears to be immersed (Fig. 19).

3. MOTION OF MATTER IN THE CENTRAL REGIONS OF GALAXIES AND NEBULAE

The pattern of matter motion within the central ellipsoidal component of massive galaxies is not directly observable. However, an understanding of the mechanism of matter motion within it can be obtained from observations of objects smaller than galaxies – namely, planetary nebulae - that are at similar stages of development. Figures 20 and 21 present examples of elongated planetary nebulae that demonstrate the character of the dispersal of matter ejected by the central excited star during similar stages of evolution. The pattern of

luminosity reflects the distribution of the expelled matter. In turn, the luminous matter, excited by magnetic field lines, reveals the distribution and intensity of the magnetic field lines capable of exciting the expelled matter.

Figure 21 shows the planetary nebulae **NGC 4361** and **Henize 3-1475**, whose polar outflows, similarly to those in spiral galaxies, begin to curve at their ends in order to reconnect with the opposite pole.

Fig. 20. Patterns of distribution of expelled matter corresponding to the stages of formation of polar bars and cones in various planetary nebulae: a - Henize 3-401 [72]; b - M2-9 Butterfly Nebula [73]; c - Mz3 Ant Nebula [74]; d - HD 44179 Red Rectangle [75]; e - Boomerang [76]; f - NGC 6302 [77].

The patterns of matter distribution within the bulge of the ellipsoidal part of galaxies are well illustrated by the structures of expelled matter observed in

spherical planetary nebulae. As can be seen in Fig. 22, which presents the

Fig. 21. Patterns of the initial bending of polar outflows in planetary nebulae: a - NGC 4361 [78]; b - Henize 3-1475 [79].

planetary nebulae **NGC 3242**, **NGC 3918**, and **NGC 7009**, in addition to polar outflows, a spherical component of the bulge is also observed, similar to that seen in elliptical galaxies. The internal structure of the bulge in these images is difficult to interpret because of the presence of dense outer shells; however, it may be assumed that the spherical shape of the central region of the nebula is caused by radial outflows from the nebula's central star.

Radial filaments are also observed in the peripheral regions of most elliptical galaxies. They create a kind of “fluffiness” in their outer zones. The radial component of the bulge is seen much more clearly in spherical planetary nebulae. In most spherical planetary nebulae, the patterns of filament distribution within them are highly complex; however, there are a number of planetary nebulae in which the radial filaments formed by the emitted matter are visible very distinctly.

Fig. 22. Spherical component of the bulge in planetary nebulae: a - NGC 3242 Призрак Юнонепа [80]; b - NGC 3918 Blue Planetary [81]; c - NGC 7009 Saturn Nebula [82].

Figure 23 presents a series of planetary nebulae in which the presence of radial emission filaments originating from the central star can be clearly observed. In the image of the nebula **NGC 6853**, whose axis of rotation lies in a plane perpendicular to the line of sight, the filaments of radial emissions are visible throughout almost the entire volume except for the polar regions.

In the nebula **NGC 6751**, the radial emissions are uniformly distributed throughout the nebular volume, which is probably related to the fact that we observe this nebula from the polar direction. The nebula **NGC 2392** presents a more complex structure; nevertheless, radial emissions can also be observed within it, forming distinct spherical zones.

Fig. 23. Patterns of radial emissions in planetary nebulae:
a - NGC 6853 Dumbbell [83]; b - NGC 6751 [84]; c - NGC 2392 Eskimo [85].

The spherical zones and the radial emissions penetrating them are most clearly observed in the nebula

NGC 6543, commonly known as the **Cat's Eye Nebula** (Fig. 24).

Fig. 24. Halo, spherical zones, and radial emissions in the Cat's Eye Nebula (NGC 6543):
a - NGC 6543 [63]; b - Cat's Eye [86].

The **Cat's Eye Nebula (NGC 6543)** is one of the best-known planetary nebulae in the sky. Located at a distance of approximately 3,000 light-years from Earth in the constellation Draco in the northern hemisphere, it was among the first planetary nebulae discovered by astronomers. Its remarkable symmetrical forms are visible in the central region of this remarkable artificially colored image, specially processed to reveal the enormous but very faint halo of gaseous matter, about three light-years in diameter, surrounding the bright planetary nebula at the center. In this composite image (Fig. 24a), radiation from nitrogen atoms is shown in red, while radiation from oxygen atoms is represented by shades of green and blue. In Fig. 24b, the

fibrous radial structure of the matter ejected by the star can be seen more clearly.

For a long time, planetary nebulae have for some reason been regarded as the final stage in the life of Sun-like stars. However, only recently have halos been discovered around some planetary nebulae, similar to the one shown above (Fig. 24), which are believed to have formed from matter ejected during earlier active stages of stellar evolution. Whereas the planetary nebula stage lasts about 10,000 years, astronomers have estimated the age of the outer fibrous part of this halo to be between 50,000 and 90,000 years [87].

Fig. 25. System of ring-shaped and radial structures in the halo of a planetary nebula NGC 6543, Cat's Eye Planetary Nebula [88].

As early as 1994, the Hubble Space Telescope revealed that Cat's Eye Nebula (NGC 6543) contains remarkable structures, including concentric gaseous shells and radial jets of rapidly moving gas. The central

region of the nebula, which in this high-resolution image obtained by the Hubble Space Telescope is visible with such fine detail, measures more than half a light-year across. The image from **Hubble's Advanced**

Camera for Surveys (ACS) reveals eleven or even more concentric rings or shells surrounding the central ellipsoidal region. Each such “ring” is in fact a projection of a thicker portion of the edge region of a sphere projected onto the observational plane — which is precisely why they appear so bright along their outer edge (Fig. 25).

It is believed that the **Cat's Eye Nebula (NGC 6543)**, like other planetary nebulae, represents the final, short-lived, but extremely bright stage in the life of a dying star. According to the prevailing view, the dying star located at the center of the nebula, after exhausting its thermonuclear fuel in the core, periodically expelled its outer layers, thereby creating a structure of concentric dust-rich shells. On the basis of observations, astronomers concluded that these stellar “eruptions” - an entire series of matter ejections - occurred at intervals of approximately 1,500 years. These “stellar convulsions” formed the dust shells, each of which contains a mass comparable to that of all the planets in our Solar System (or about 1% of the Sun's mass). Astronomers were surprised by the fact that episodes of matter ejection near the end of a star's life could recur every 1,500 years. Several explanations for this phenomenon have been proposed:

- the action of cycles of magnetic activity similar to the activity cycles of our own Sun;
- the possible influence of a stellar companion (or companions) orbiting the dying star;
- stellar pulsations;
- the possibility that the matter was expelled only once, while the “ring system” formed later due to the development of waves within the already ejected material [89, 90].

However, if one compares images of this nebula obtained by the Hubble Space Telescope in 1994, 1997, 2000, and 2002, one can notice their continuing expansion. This indicates that the formation of these rings is most likely caused by a different mechanism and represents a regular phenomenon rather than an exception, and that the process is still continuing at the present time.

The mechanism responsible for the formation of this beautiful and complex pattern has not yet been examined in sufficient detail.

We believe that the appearance of distinct zones of differing luminosity is more likely caused by the separation of matter ejected radially from the excited center of a galaxy or star. The heavier expelled components form the zones closest to the nucleus, while the lighter components form the more distant concentric zones.

4. ANOTHER REMARK ON THE STRUCTURE OF STARS AND COMETS

The existence of stars with variable luminosity, the periodic explosions of supernovae and novae, as well as the repeated outburst of 17P/Holmes on October 23–24, 2007, cast doubt on the validity of the conclusion that such pulsations are caused solely by thermonuclear reactions in the cores of these objects coming to an end. Rather, these phenomena seem to indicate interactions with invisible periodic energy flows in cosmic space that a star encounters during its motion. We

assume that such exciting flows are streams of magnetic field lines emitted by various objects in the Universe (The role of magnetic flows [39, 40, 91]).

5. CONCLUSION

It is impossible to discuss all the accumulated unique observational facts within the scope of a short article; however, the analysis carried out allows the following principal conclusions to be drawn:

- Nature has provided us with a unique microscope of cosmic scale, within which phenomena inaccessible to investigation at the microscopic level can be studied;
- All dense matter in the Universe is accumulated in the form of spherical vortices and exists within halos generated by the electromagnetic fields of the vortices themselves;
- The various observable patterns of the vortex state of matter in space reflect the evolutionary stages of the object under investigation at the particular moment in time at which we observe (or record) it;
- The observed patterns of matter motion in individual accumulations indicate the absence of a dense medium in the regions where these processes occur, even in the centers of the accumulations;
- Cosmic space is permeated by streams of magnetic field lines generated by objects of various scales in the Universe (both by the Universe itself and by its individual objects), interactions with which are manifested in the outbursts of variable stars, supernovae, and comets (in particular, the outburst of 17P/Holmes that occurred on October 24, 2007);
- The recorded vortex patterns of distributed matter in space reflect the stage of the pulsational character of the observed object's life that has reached us;
- All observed facts indicate the existence of a pulsational character in the existence of the Universe itself, similar to that observed in the Sun, whose pulsation period, as discovered by Academician Andrei Severny in 1974, is 160 minutes. In this case, the observed expansion of the Universe is caused namely by this stage of the pulsation expansion, but not from a “single point”; rather, it proceeds from a particular state of the system.

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References

1. Lemaître, G.: The Evolution of the Universe: discussion, *Nature* 128: suppl.: 704, (1931)
2. Milyus A., Milyuvnev, V., Milyute E., Once more about the Origin of Chemical Elements. XXI Mendeleev Congress on General and Applied Chemistry, Book 1: Fundamental Problems of Chemical Science (2019)
3. Milyute, E., Milyus, A., Vortex Dynamics of Substance in an Isolated Spheroidal Vortex and its Relationship with a Charge. *DIZZW*, Nr. 48 (2023)
4. Milyute, E., Milyuvnev, V., Milyus, A., Some Questions of Dynamics of Substance in the Spherical

- Vortex. In: Proceeding of IUTAM Symposium "Hamiltonian Dynamics, Vortex Structures, Turbulence", Moscow, (2008)
5. <http://www.solstation.com/xobjects/great-voi.htm>
 6. Munch, G., Mampaso, A., Sanchez, F.: *The Universe at Large Key: Key Issues in Astronomy and Cosmology*, Cambridge University Press (1997)
 7. Ambartsumian, V.A., 11th Solvay Conference on Structure and Evolution of the Universe, (R.Stoops), Bruxelles (1958)
 8. Ambartsumian, V.A., *Structure and Evolution of Galaxies*, Proc. 13th Conf. on Physics, University of Brussels, New York, Wiley Interscience (1965)
 9. *The Universe, Astronomy, Philosophy*, MGU, Moscow (1988) (In Russian)
 10. <https://science.nasa.gov/missions/hubble/hubble-zooms-in-on-heart-of-mystery-comet/>
 11. https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/hubble/news/hubble-holmes.html
 12. Newspaper "Izvestija", №163, 10.09.2007
 13. <http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1162469/eng>
 14. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/asteroids-comets-and-meteors/comets/81p-wild/in-depth/>
 15. <http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1197204>
 16. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/stardust/photo/cometwild2.html>
 17. <https://www.astrochem.org/docs/Brownlee%20%282004%29-Science.pdf>
 18. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/stardust/home/index.html>
 19. http://vivovoco.astronet.ru/VV/JOURNAL/NATURE/09_06/STARDUST.HTM
 20. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/stardust/news/news113.html>
 21. <https://www.universetoday.com/40364/mini-comets-ejected-from-comet-holmes-caused-outburst/>
 22. https://spaceweather.com/comets/gallery_holmes_page11.htm
 23. <http://annesastronomynews.com/photo-gallery-ii/nebulae-clouds/abell-39/>
 24. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Owl_Nebula
 25. <https://esahubble.org/images/heic0405b/>
 26. CometHolmes: <http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1224339>
 27. Novopashin S., Radchenko V.V., Sakharov S. Three-Dimensional Striations of a Glow Discharge, *IEEE Transactions on Plasma sciences*, V. 36, Issue 4, August 2008, pp. 998-999
 28. NGC 7144: <http://astronomia.zcu.cz/objekty/ngc7144>
 29. NGC 3379: <https://www.messier-objects.com/messier-105/>
 30. NGC 221: https://cseligman.com/text/stars/messier_galaxies.htm
 31. NGC 533: https://kosmoved.ru/get_ngcic.php?ID=NGC-533&lang=eng
 32. NGC 4697: <http://blackholes.stardate.org/objects/factsheet-NGC-4697.html>
 33. NGC 584: <https://thesky-live.com/sky/deepsky/ngc584-object>
 34. NGC 3610: <https://cseligman.com/text/atlas/ngc36.htm>
 35. NGC 4026: <https://thesky-live.com/sky/deepsky/ngc4026-object> https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_4026
 36. NGC 3867: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_3867
 37. NGS 108: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_108
 38. NGC 4572: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NGC_4572_PanS.jpg
 39. Milyuvene, V., Milyute, E., Milyus, A., A new look at a vortical dynamics of a substance in the Universe. In: *Proceeding of IUTAM Symposium "150 years of Vortex Dynamics"*, Springer (2008)
 40. Milyus A., Milyuvene V., Milyute E. *On Vortical Dynamics of Substance of Objects of the Universe // XX Mendeleev Congress on General and Applied Chemistry*, Book 1, Ekaterinburg, Russia (2016)
 41. NGC 3782: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_3782
 42. NGC 3509: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_3509
 43. NGS 1720: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_1720
 44. NGC 7479: <http://www.capella-observatory.com/ImageHTMLs/Galaxies/NGC7479.htm>
 45. NGC 6701: <https://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/data/GOALS/galaxies/NGC6701.html>
 46. NGC 762: <https://cseligman.com/text/atlas/ngc7a.htm>
 47. NGC 2935: https://cgs.obs.carnegiescience.edu/CGS/object_html_pages/NGC2935.html
 48. NGC 6782: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_6782
 49. NGC 5383: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NGC_5383_SDSS2.jpg
 50. NGC 986: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_986
 51. NGC 2442: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_2442_and_NGC_2443
 52. NGC 1300: http://www.astroimage.info/images/deepsky/galaxy/pages/n1300jrf_filtered.htm
 53. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Big_Bang
 54. NGC 2859: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_2859
 55. NGC 1269: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_1269
 56. NGC 4643: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_4643
 57. NGC 4440: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_4440
 58. NGC 1433: <https://pages.astronomy.ua.edu/gifimages/ngc1433.html>
 59. NGC 266: <https://www.astrobin.com/qyznmd/0/?nc=all>
 60. NGC 3992: https://www.wikiwand.com/ce/NGC_3992
 61. NGC 3351: <https://apod.nasa.gov/apod/ap070314.html>
 62. NGC 5307: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_5307
 63. NGC 6543: <http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1179510>

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|-------------------|---|---|---|
| 64. NGC 1365 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1221346 | 78. NGC 4631 | https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_4361 |
| 65. NGC 6872 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1163124 | 79. Henize 3-1475: | https://esahubble.org/news/heic0308/ |
| 66. UGS 10214: | https://esahubble.org/images/heic0206e/ | 80. NGC 3242 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1209092 |
| 67. NGC 1300 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1201857 | 81. NGC 3918: | https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/NGC_3918 |
| 68. NGC 5194 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1225467 | 82. NGC 7009 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1163665 |
| 69. NGC 4736 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1168902 | 83. NGC 6853 Dumbbell: | https://www.universetoday.com/33035/messier-27-dumbbell-nebula/ |
| 70. NGC 4319 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1180026 | 84. NGC 6751 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1205214 |
| 71. NGC 1350 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1208394 | 85. NGC 2392 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1214787 |
| 72. Henize 3-401: | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1178678 | 86. NGC 6543 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1665065 |
| 73. M2-9 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1206216 | 87. http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1194578 | |
| 74. Mz 3 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1205432 | 88. NGC 6543 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1221996 |
| 75. HD 44179: | https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Red_Rectangle_Nebula | 89. http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1199550/ | |
| 76. Boomerang | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1225326 | 90. https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/images/pia16009-dying-star-creates-fantasy-like-sculpture-of-gas-and-dust | |
| 77. NGC 6302 | http://www.astronet.ru/db/msg/1221803 | 91. Milyuvene V., Milyute E., Milyus A. The role of magnetic fluxes in excitation of luminescence of cosmic objects. In print. | |